

An Evaluation of the Effectiveness of the SATRE Specification to Support the Creation of a Federated Information Governance Framework

PANORAMA Work Package 1 Final Report

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Executive Summary

This report summarises the findings from PANORAMA Work Package 1, which aimed to test the suitability and limitations of the [Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments](#) (SATRE) specification to support the creation of a federated Information Governance (IG) framework across the three north of England NHS sub-national Secure Data Environments covering the north of England: North East & North Cumbria NHS SDE, North West NHS SDE, and Yorkshire & Humber SDE, with the Work Package facilitated by researchers at the University of Sheffield. We trialled an approach based on the concept of equivalence proposed by the Scottish Safe Haven Network and UK TRE Community using the SATRE specification.

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The trial found that taking time to agree definitions of key terminologies at the outset of federated IG work is essential due to variance in interpretation of key terms, which poses a significant barrier to progression. The SATRE tool can provide a useful structure for federating organisations when establishing essential requirements to progress towards an organisation-level shared IG, particularly around information and data management. However, SATRE on its own cannot (yet) establish a federated IG framework, and our methodology omitted an important step in progressing towards organisation-level federation, namely a detailed examination of scope and the concept of ‘federation’ broadly and specifically within the context of federated analytics. We offer improvements to the SATRE IG criteria to make them more relevant to federation, including improving clarity, requesting additional guidance for justification of scores, and altering the structure to break broad topics into specific, tangible measures. Recommendations are also made for ongoing assurance monitoring, such as assigning a responsible team within the federation to conduct reviews to monitor change at least annually. We also outline the next steps required for organisations to create a federated IG framework.

1. Background: The need for Federated Information Governance (IG)

Trusted Research Environments (TREs) – also known as Safe Havens or Secure Data Environments (SDEs) – are highly secure, controlled research computing and analysis platforms and services allowing approved researchers to access and analyse sensitive data without data leaving the environment. They maintain robust information security management standards (e.g. ISO27001, NHS Digital Security Protection Toolkit, Digital Economy Act), and often comply with other frameworks (e.g. the Five Safes framework, Caldicott Guardian principles) to ensure data is used ethically and only for its intended purpose. Many TREs have enabled faster access to data for research by securing overall research ethics (including rigorous public benefit requirements and other requirements around confidentiality and privacy); though these may take many months (or years) to receive, TREs can then operate local governance pathways to review individual research projects, streamlining researcher access to data whilst still requiring the robust evidence required to access specific research project data.

However, because TREs are largely linked to a single organisation’s data – or a number of organisations within a specific context, such as a region or sector – and have been designed on the distinct requirements of the organisation(s), data still remains in silos. Organisations are reluctant to share data between TREs, borne out of concerns that the technology, security and operational processes of one TRE may not be identical to its own. Whilst an individual TRE may have streamlined ethics for its data, applying for data access across multiple TREs will still require individual applications to each site and protracted negotiations related to data sharing between the TREs. Likewise, agreements for data sharing across the individual TREs relate only to a specific research project so researchers face a significant burden of negotiations and requirements for each piece of research they wish to undertake. The resourcing required to support this per-project approach to cross-organisational data access for researchers, organisations and TREs is substantial, and is a major barrier to enabling research that can lead to life-changing insights across regional or domain footprints.

1.1. The NHS Secure Data Environment Network

The [NHS Secure Data Environment \(SDE\) Network](#) was founded in 2022 to improve researcher access to routinely-collected, secondary use health and social care data, and overcome many of the challenges created by the existence of silos of sensitive health data in England. A key benefit of the NHS SDE programme is the streamlining of ethics and IG processes for access to linked data from different providers, removing the need for researchers to complete individual access requests to multiple organisations. This model has been successfully implemented in the other UK nations with SAILDatabank (Wales), Scottish Safe Haven Network (Scotland) and the Honest Broker Service (Northern Ireland). Although established as regional data organisations, the aim of the NHS SDE network is to create an England-wide federation supporting cross-regional access to health and social care data.

Investing in data connectivity and interoperability holds the potential to unlock valuable insights, enable research collaborations, and enhance the delivery of healthcare services. However, it is crucial to ensure that these efforts are accompanied by strong governance mechanisms to protect research participant's privacy and maintain data security [1]. Whilst the aim of the NHS SDE Network is to support network-wide research at scale, at this stage, researcher's access to multi-SDE data for analysis is still on a project-by-project basis. This is the case for most 'federations' in the UK (and, indeed, globally), with each organisation or data controller requiring multi-organisational project-specific approvals that do not yet streamline access to data for research at an organisational level.

As one of the DARE UK TRevolution Early Adopters, the PANORAMA project aims to improve researcher access to sensitive health and social care data for a population of 15.5 million in the North of England. Consisting of the three northern England NHS SDEs (North East & North Cumbria SDE, North West SDE, and Yorkshire & Humber SDE), in collaboration with researchers at the University of Sheffield. PANORAMA aims to test the SATRE evaluation tool in the context of enabling a federated information governance framework (defined as an overarching structure describing the general terms and conditions for governance), and create a methodology that could be used by other organisations to support federated information governance.

1.2. IG challenges and the SATRE Specification

Establishing wholesale agreements and permissions to support different types of federated analytics between Trusted Research Environments (TREs) would streamline the process for researchers, and avoid organisations repeating governance agreements for each project. DARE UK's [Federated Architecture Blueprint](#) and the World Economic Forum's [Technology Convergence Report](#) have already proposed that the federation technologies available, such as Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), should enable governance frameworks to be created which extend, rather than replace, the IG already in place within TREs, resulting in robust over-arching federated IG without disrupting local policies and processes.

However, organisations must be assured that data handling practices are equally secure and governance principles consistently applied across the SDEs involved, and key legal and organisational challenges, for instance agreeing how to determine user access, and division of benefits and commercial value, must be overcome [2, 3, 4, 5]. As federated working between TREs is a comparatively new area, formal guidance and a structured methodology to create a federated IG framework do not currently exist. Whilst other IG frameworks may be helpful (for instance, the NHS England [Information Governance Framework for Integrated Health and Care: Shared Care Records](#), they have limited scope, addressing IG only for organisations

within a single overarching entity (e.g. NHS healthcare organisations) and for a single, specific purpose (patient care).

Although, there is a tool that may enable federated working. The [Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments \(SATRE\) specification](#) was established to harmonise operational inconsistencies between TREs, and provide greater assurance to data providers and the public that organisations had achieved certain standards of safe data management. In particular, the goal of SATRE is to ‘standardise the capabilities of TREs, making it easier for users, operators, and developers to work with sensitive data, and making the operation of TREs more transparent to data owners and the general public’. It enables self-assessment by TREs across the three core pillars of information governance, computing technology, and data management, plus supporting capabilities, and is specific to TREs but agnostic of the type of TRE or its national location.

Due to its prescriptive guidance and completeness of coverage across critical infrastructure and operations supporting sensitive data research, the [Sudlow Review](#) notes that SATRE can become the UK-wide standard and accreditation for TREs facilitating sensitive data research. By standardising the capabilities of TREs, and by enabling the evaluation of a TRE against a standard, PANORAMA considers whether SATRE has the potential to address the challenge of different organisations’ concerns about incongruity in information governance, computing technology and security and data management standards, as well as the operational processes supporting these capabilities, between TREs.

1.3. PANORAMA Federated IG Aims and Objectives

The PANORAMA project aims to establish whether compliance with SATRE (version 1.0) provides sufficient evidence of organisational alignment for TREs to implement a shared information governance framework to support federated analytics.

Specifically, the objectives are to identify a methodology utilising SATRE that could be reproducible, interoperable and extendable to any group of organisations aiming to federate information governance at an organisational level.

This report presents the outcomes of the original conceptual methodology against the reality of creating a shared IG framework, and lessons learnt from this process in a real-world context. We present a revised methodology for TREs aiming to create a formal IG framework, recommendations for revising and refining SATRE and practical guidance for future use.

2. Original federated IG methodology

The concept of ‘equivalence’ is one used in many other disciplines, from manufacturing to translation studies. It is a formal recognition of the fact that things being examined have the same amount, value, purpose or qualities, and that those things are therefore interchangeable. Pharmaceutical product equivalence, for example, is critical for generic drug development and use [4]. Equivalence concepts in manufacturing establish whether measurements can be considered the equal, and to what degree there can be an acceptable level of variation but still be considered ‘the same’ [6].

Stemming from equivalence is the idea of ‘tolerance’, again a concept already familiar to pharmaceutical product manufacturing. When comparing drugs, there may be statistical

differences in performance but that difference is not actually practically meaningful, with tolerance describing the limits of acceptance for that difference between products [7]. It is not a fixed, prescribable unit for implementation, but rather something which must be determined by each federation, and should be risk based, with areas of higher risk allowing only small practical differences whilst lower risk areas can have broader margins of acceptance [8].

The original methodology for PANORAMA was framed based on initial work by other organisations attempting to create a formal federated, interoperable network of TREs and enabling federated information governance. As previously mentioned DARE UK and the World Economic Forum have proposed that federation *technologies* should enable governance frameworks to be created which extend, rather than replace, the IG already in place within TREs. Yet the Scottish Safe Haven Network and the UK TRE Community Information Governance Interest Group ([UK TRE Community Quarterly Meeting Feb 2025](#)) have presented approaches to, and early findings on, operationalising federation that could be utilised without the need for technical solutions.

Whilst PANORAMA also tested technologies that can enable federation (i.e., 5 Safes Test Execution Service (5STES) and Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs (SACRO)), for this work package, we used the latter approach of examining organisation-level IG frameworks within the context of existing practices.

The conceptual methodology proposed at the start of the project to enable a federated IG framework was to:

1. Undertake individual SATRE assessments across the PANORAMA partners.
2. Undertake a comparison exercise of the individual SATRE assessments.
3. Undertake an 'equivalence' exercise comparing the differences identified in the SATRE comparison exercise.
4. From the equivalence exercise, agree tolerance levels and address areas that would need to be remediated due to variation outside of agreed tolerance.
5. Once remediated, agreeing a federated IG framework.

The above was presented in an initial 'Pre-equivalence' workshop to IG professionals across the partners to agree the approach and steps, above. However, at this stage, Organisation 2, with Organisation 3 agreeing, questioned the utility in creating a 'federated IG framework' as that is already a recognised process of creating a Data Processing Impact Assessment and other accompanying documents such as Data Sharing Agreements, Information Sharing Agreements, etc. What became apparent in the course of this early session was that IG professionals focussed very heavily on the legal basis for data sharing (in any form, both pooling of data as well as federated analytics) and the requirement for a DPIA and other documents. Additionally, because all the PANORAMA partners are contained within the same network (the NHS England Secure Data Environment Network), with a central oversight body (NHS England Data for Research and Development) and the formal deliverable of creating interoperability between the SDEs, federation is a required deliverable rather than an aim. This critical difference between requirement and intention was a key factor in revising the original methodological approach.

The second factor in revising the methodological approach also came out of this pre-workshop, in which the research team realised that the terminology and language that they were using was different from the terminology and language IG professionals were using. A key example of this was the term 'framework'. The PANORAMA research team facilitating Work Package 1 were using 'framework' in a more generalised sense closer to 'Principles' whereas the professionals were using 'framework' in a more specific sense closer to 'Agreement'. We define these terms as follows:

- **Principles** are highly general and focus on 'why' or 'should be done' in an ideal sense. Whilst they promote consistency, they lack detailed implementation instructions. They are not legally binding, but they may form the foundation for more concrete documents.
- **Frameworks** are overarching structures that set out the general terms and procedures under which future, specific agreements can be made. They are a set of practices rolled together and provide a mechanism to streamline future agreements without needing to renegotiate fundamental provisions each time. They formally set out the terms and conditions for future transactions.
- **Agreements** are specific understandings between parties that define precise obligations and terms for specific provisioning of services. They are highly detailed, covering the deliverables and specific obligations for particular transactions.

A third point that arose from this initial pre-workshop was agreeing the context of the equivalence exercise. The research team observed that operational IG professionals situated discussions in the current IG approach based on specific projects, e.g., the specific legal and regulatory obligations, the specific data processing activities, the unique data types and sensitivities, and the specific risks associated. The broad aim of PANORAMA Work Package 1 was to consider an organisation-wide approach to federated IG, but this was not explicitly stated. Therefore, there was misalignment between the research team and professionals, which needed to be addressed before a SATRE equivalence exercise could be undertaken.

Finally, on the aspect of equivalence, the research team inferred from the earlier work by the [Scottish Safe Haven Network](#) that SATRE equivalence was a sufficient enabler of federation; that is, the outcome that each partner met the SATRE standard and were therefore 'the same' (even if operational practices differed), and that this equivalence was sufficient in and of itself to establish a federated IG framework. However, the IG professionals consulted in PANORAMA articulated that 'sameness' was not necessarily sufficient. Therefore, the research team identified both 'sameness' as well as the degree to which variation/difference could be tolerated within a federation should be captured, along with the supporting evidence required to establish sameness and tolerance, and the additional requirements needed beyond a SATRE assessment to implement a federated IG framework.

3. Revised federated IG methodology

Given the feedback on original methodological scope, we revised our equivalence methodology to focus on de-coupling the partners from the specific deliverable of 'federation' for the NHS SDE network and re-framed it within the context of a cross-nation federation (such as the UK Government's [Health Data Research Service](#) announced in April 2025), and

narrowing the scope of the equivalence to the SATRE Information Governance capability to examine each criterion in detail. By modifying the scope of the equivalency exercise, we were able to abstract partners to a level where they were able to consider SATRE independent of the operational implementation of federated information governance within the context of the SDE network.

Additionally, we incorporated feedback by expanding the equivalence exercise to evaluate SATRE generally to address its application within a federated context. This resulted in three further inclusions to the equivalence exercise: first, we asked whether each criterion listed was relevant to IG; second, we considered whether the SATRE statement and guidance across all criteria in the IG section was appropriate and useful or what needed to change to make it so; and third, we considered whether each criterion was essential to federation. For the PANORAMA context specifically, we considered what documentation or information would be required to enable a federated IG agreement. Finally, we aimed to address a current gap in approaches to federation, namely, ongoing monitoring of compliance. Researchers from the PANORAMA project joined the regular SATRE team meetings.

The revised Methodology is as follows:

1. Undertake individual SATRE assessments.
2. Undertake a comparison exercise of the individual SATRE assessments.
3. To set out an approach to establishing a shared language around governance and federation between PANORAMA partners.
4. Undertake an 'equivalence' exercise comparing the differences identified in the SATRE comparison exercise, and determine tolerance for each criterion.
5. Identify the additional steps required before a federated Information Governance framework can be implemented at an organisational level.
6. Contribute to the expansion of SATRE to support federation competencies and capabilities within and between organisations.
7. Design a process for monitoring equivalence over time.

3.1. Step 1: Undertake individual SATRE assessments

Whilst each organisation had undertaken SATRE-SDE assessments (i.e., a specific variation of SATRE specifically designed for the NHS SDE network), we asked partners to undertake a full SATRE specification to focus on the widest range of interoperability standards. Each organisation completed the self-assessment and used the template provided on the SATRE [website](#).

3.2. Step 2: Compile individual SATRE assessments

Each partner provided its full SATRE self-assessment to the research team who collated them and produced a heatmap of the results, with scores of 2 ('Satisfied') colour-coded green, scores of 1 ('Sufficient') colour-coded yellow, scores of 0 ('Not met') colour-coded red, and scores of N/A ('Not applicable to a TRE') colour-coded blue.

3.3. Step 3: Define terms to establish a common vocabulary

As discussed above, from the pre-equivalence workshop, it became apparent that the research team and IG professionals were using different terminology. Before the equivalence workshop, therefore, the research team introduced a new workshop to define terms. Key terms were selected and, as a pre-workshop exercise, each partner was asked to provide their individual definitions. During the terminology workshop, partners were asked to discuss the individual definitions and come to a consensus on the terms. Those terms would then be consulted as necessary during the equivalence exercise.

The terms selected were as follows:

- Data Governance
- Information Governance
- Trust
- Tolerance
- Equivalence
- Ethics
- Federation

We selected these terms either because they seemed to be problematic in a review of the recording and transcription of the pre-workshop (see 'Original Methodology', above), or because they were frequently used words during the pre-workshop.

3.4. Step 4: Undertake equivalence exercise

The equivalence exercise was organised as a workshop between the partners and facilitated by the PANORAMA research team. With this work package focussed on Information Governance, we facilitated the Information Governance capability within SATRE with IG professionals. Other equivalency workshops (e.g. Data Management, Computing Technology and Supporting Capabilities) should be held with the subject-matter experts for those domains to finalise a federated IG framework.

The order for discussion of the SATRE criteria in the full workshop was debated. The option to prioritise criteria where one or more SDEs were red or yellow (assessment score of 0 or 1) was considered by the research team in the original methodology because these aspects would be the most obvious areas for 'remediation'. However, given the feedback in the pre-workshop that SATRE may not be useful at all to support a federated IG framework since a common score across all partners may still not indicate 'equivalence', we opted to proceed through each criterion in numerical order.

For each criterion, the group first agreed if it was critical to federation, then, for those which were, we assessed for areas of congruence, difference and equivalence in current governance frameworks. Where scores differed, it was agreed if this was within an acceptable tolerance or whether actions were needed to treat the difference.

In the equivalence exercise, the PANORAMA partners also discussed each SATRE statement and guidance, reviewing whether the statement and guidance were clear, or if there were comments or improvements that could be made to the statement and guidance

3.5. Step 5: Identify additional steps required to federate

One particular issue that emerged from the pre-workshop was the need to define the additional documentation or requirements to federate at the organisational level. So, the

research team asked partners to list what evidence would be required to demonstrate compliance and what may/may not be required to include in a federated IG agreement. We also considered the wider IG work that would be needed between each organisation and its data providers, and the process of bringing all the findings together to generate the agreements to support federation. Although some of this was incorporated into the equivalence exercise, we see this as a distinct, separate requirement for PANORAMA partners to articulate the specific requirements they would need to federate

3.6. Step 6: Expansion of SATRE

One aim of PANORAMA was to suggest improvements to the SATRE assessment to support federation. In particular, the project sought to identify the criteria which applied to organisational-level IG, so are key to federation, as opposed to criteria which would be assessed at a project-level. This need was further highlighted from the pre-workshop as the partners described obvious shortfalls in the assessment when applied to federation.

Therefore, in the equivalence exercise the group determined which criteria were critical for federation, and which were not relevant (even though they may be important within an organisation), to highlight which criteria would be most suitable for adaptation and expansion to support a federation capability.

3.7. Step 7: Monitor equivalence over time

One aspect of federation that has not been addressed is maintaining and monitoring equivalence over time or in the context of significant policy or other changes. The research team identified this as an important consideration to ensure parties continue to maintain SATRE compliance as well as the frameworks and agreements in place after a federation is formalised. Thus, we asked IG professionals what would be required to monitor and maintain equivalence within the scope of the federated IG framework.

4. Analysis and discussion

We present the results of our revised methodology below, including findings when assembling the shared heatmap, outputs from the shared vocabulary exercise and equivalence exercise, and additional contributions such as further requirements for federation.

Additionally, several recommendations are made to improve the use and content of SATRE, ranging from addressing scoring variability, to improving specificity within criteria. These are listed in [Appendix C](#).

4.1. Individual SATRE assessments and SATRE comparison

As previously mentioned, although each organisation had completed the NHS SDE SATRE specification, we expanded the request to include the full SATRE specification to improve interoperability and reproducibility for other organisations. The exercise consists of a self-assessment and for most organisations will require multiple specialist teams to support its completion. Organisations should set aside at least two full working days for the whole assessment.

For the federation comparison exercise, partners shared their individual responses to the research team, who compiled them into a single document. They produced a heatmap in order

to visualise the variation between the SDEs. We omitted the ‘Response’ and ‘Improvements’ columns of the SATRE template to facilitate conversation between partners in the workshops. However, other organisations may wish to include these in a heatmap and pre-circulate for review ahead of an equivalence workshop to identify areas for discussion.

The full heatmap is included in [Appendix B](#).

A particular issue of variance between SDEs for their SATRE self-assessments was the interpretation of a score of ‘0’ versus a score of ‘N/A’ (figure 3). These occurred only for ‘recommended’ or ‘optional’ criteria, reflecting local differences in how unachieved criteria which are not mandatory should be scored.

The SATRE criteria were designed to cover all aspects relevant to operating a TRE, and TREs do not have to achieve non-mandatory criteria to be compliant. On this basis, it is arguably more transparent for TREs to declare if they do not have a feature (score ‘0’) rather than deem it ‘not applicable’. Thus, clearer guidance is needed to describe the instances when the score of ‘N/A’ should be applied, to support consistent interpretation.

Figure 3: Non-critical criteria where scores were 0 or N/A

Section	Item	Statement	Guidance	Importance	Critical to federation?	SDE1	SDE2	SDE3	Challenges in establishing equivalence
1	Information governance	1.6.5. You should accept proof of relevant training certifications from trusted third parties.	You might choose to trust certifications provided by known training providers or your institution's partner organisations.	Recommended		Red	Blue	Yellow	
2	Information governance	1.6.6. You could have a training platform capable of delivering online training in a variety of formats.	This could be a simple content delivery platform or a more comprehensive LMS platform. It could also include a range of multimedia delivery formats, and accessible training modules for those...	Optional	No	Yellow	Blue	Red	
3	Information governance	1.6.7. You could implement a learning management system (LMS) to manage courses and deliver training as required.	Where possible an LMS should support a variety of course content and testing.	Optional	No	Yellow	Blue	Red	
4	Information governance	1.6.8. You could ensure that any courses you use are available in standard, transferable formats.	Support for standard formats such as SCORM allows courses to be shared between providers.	Optional	No	Yellow	Green	Red	
5	Information governance	1.6.9. You could keep historical copies of courses in order to demonstrate competency at a given point in time.	Information asset owners and regulators may be required to audit historical records, *e.g.* for clinical trials. It may be necessary to retain copies of superseded training along with versions of certifications within the	Optional	No	Yellow	Green	Red	
6					No	Yellow	Green	Red	

The above figure presents some of the SATRE criteria identified as non-critical to federation. Although these items are not essential for enabling federation, they were still examined because all SATRE criteria contribute to the effective operation of a TRE/SDE. Discussions across the three SDEs highlighted uncertainty around when a criterion should be scored as 0 or marked as not applicable, indicating a need for clearer guidance to support consistent interpretation.

4.2. Defining terms to establish a common vocabulary

Previous work on federation in healthcare research has reported a lack of clarity over important terminology, which has slowed the process of data provision [17]. In PANORAMA, it was again evident that local variations in the interpretation of key terminologies presented a barrier to federated IG. The full list of terms, individual definitions and consensus definitions are provided in [Appendix A](#). Notable outcomes are discussed below.

4.2.1. Definitions that were too broad

Participants identified that two of the terms were too broad when considered in the context of implementing a federated IG framework, and recommended additional terms with narrower scope for definition:

Original Term for Definition	Additional Definitions Needed
Federation	Federated Analytics
Ethics	Data Ethics
	Research Ethics

Table 1: terms originally planned for definition, and the additional terms identified which required definition

For ‘ethics’, both Data Ethics and Research Ethics were deemed relevant to federation, and thus definitions of both terms would need to be agreed. The definitions for these terms offered by the UK government and UKRI were accepted (see Table A2 in [Appendix A](#)).

Although the term ‘Federated’ was further refined to ‘Federated Analytics’, the discovery exercise was still unable to agree on a definition. Definitions from other researchers and the TRE network were discussed (see Table A3 in [Appendix A](#)). However, the statement in the TRE Glossary definition that federated analytics ‘maintains data privacy’ was opined to be an assumption which cannot be substantiated without robust information governance assessment of any such process. In addition, all definitions reference the raw data not being moved, but, largely due to federated analytics being a comparatively new topic in TREs, different people hold different understandings of the term, with many using it as an umbrella term which can encompass data pooling.

This variation in understanding of the term ‘Federated Analytics’ can be addressed more easily at a project specific level, because the project itself (including the data type and analytical tooling) defines the scope. But to implement an overarching federated IG framework, the need for precisely defined terminologies agreed between all participating organisations becomes critical. Without this, there is a risk that governance agreements cannot be progressed.

For this reason, it was agreed that organisations working to implement federated analytics would need to define each of the terms:

- Federated summary statistics
- Federated analytics
- Federated pooling
- Federated learning

4.2.2. Community-driven versus network-driven definitions

Many of the key terms around federated analytics and federated information governance lack any definition from a national level, nor are they legal terms with the associated authoritative interpretation that would afford.

Whilst network-driven definitions can provide clarity and uniformity, this discovery exercise revealed an unmet need for definitions of many terms, as well as disagreement with existing Network definitions when applied in a real-world setting.

Only three definitions suggested by SDEs were taken from the [TRevolution Collaboration Cafe, 4 November 2025](#) and [UK TRE Glossary](#). These were:

- Federation
- Information Governance
- Data Governance

Of these, only the definition for 'Federation' was accepted as a consensus definition, with a minor change to wording made (in bold): 'A *grouping of organisations with their own policies and assets (e.g. datasets or computing resources) who agree to allow use of those assets by the broader group but without the **row level data** leaving control or ownership of the organisation*'.

The recommendation to replace 'assets' with 'row level data' was made to explicate that, whilst the granular data does not leave the organisation, there is movement of aggregate data within a federation.

In the other two instances ('Information Governance' and 'Data Governance'), the TRE definitions were felt to lack detail and accuracy when applied to a real-world setting, or to be descriptive rather than definitive in nature.

In the absence of formally agreed terms at a national (or international level), it is therefore a fundamental early step for organisations working together on federated IG that they establish shared, agreed vocabulary. Where terms require formal definition or recognition to enable transparency, reproducibility and federation, raising this need to organisations such as the UK TRE Community, DARE UK or the Pan-UK Data Governance Steering Group and escalation to the relevant national bodies responsible for the safety of sensitive data (for instance in the UK, the Information Commissioner's Office and the Department of Health and Social Care) may be appropriate.

4.2.3. Additional definitions

As discussed in 'Original Methodology', the discovery exercise revealed a significant difference in interpretation of the term 'Information Governance framework' between the research team and the IG professionals within NHS SDEs. It was thus not possible to progress to the equivalence exercise without agreeing the definitions of 'Information governance framework in a federation' and 'federated IG agreement' (see Table A4 in [Appendix A](#)).

The principle finding when defining these terms was that an IG framework would describe the requirements to be met (for example, Common Law Duty of Confidentiality, data controllership), whereas the agreement would be the detailed document(s) to meet those requirements.

4.2.4. Obtaining agreement on definitions from organisations

The drive for federation typically comes from operational teams within the TREs, seeking ways to manage a high workload of research projects. This creates a potential point of tension, where individuals working directly on federation agree definitions but they have not been defined at an organisational level. It is recommended, therefore, that a multi-stage approach to establishing a shared vocabulary be taken, where operations teams work to define terminologies before reporting the findings back for sign-off by their respective organisations, if these exist (in the NHS SDE Network, for example, this would be the IG and Ethics Community of Practice). In the absence of formal communities of practice or governing bodies, the senior responsible persons across the federation should formally agree terminology.

4.3. Equivalence exercise and workshop to refine and adapt SATRE for federation

Prior to the equivalence workshop, the research team considered the most efficient way to combine Steps 4-6 of their revised methodology. They created a revised heatmap to include the aspects covered in those steps.

Figure 2: Shared heatmap template

Section	Item	Statement	Guidance	Importance	Critical to federation?	Notes/Justification	Evidence needed to support federation	SDE1	SDE2	SDE2	Challenges in establishing equivalence
Information governance	1.1.1.	You must gather and monitor the information governance requirements needed to fulfil any legal, regulatory and ethical standards.	Requirements will come from a variety of sources including legislation, contractual obligations and ethical standards. Requirements must be monitored to ensure the TRE controls remain appropriate.	Mandatory							
Information governance	1.1.2.	You must ensure controls are implemented to ensure the requirements are met.	Control implementation should be systematic and directly aligned to the internal and stakeholder requirements.	Mandatory							
Information governance	1.1.3.	You must ensure there are adequate resources to meet information governance requirements.	Ensuring information governance controls are suitable and enforced requires an investment of funding and people appropriate to the size of the TRE.	Mandatory							
Information governance	1.2.1.	You must ensure that changes to policies and standard operating procedures can only be made by trusted individuals.	It is important to ensure that policies and SOPs are relevant, up-to-date and carefully controlled to maintain the integrity and security of your TRE organisation.	Mandatory							

Figure 2 presents an example of the heatmap template used during the workshop to record information governance requirements, related guidance, evidence needed for federation, and challenges in demonstrating equivalence across Secure Data Environments. The template also supported identifying whether each SATRE criterion was considered critical to federation across the three participating SDEs.

Since PANORAMA aimed to improve the SATRE tool for supporting federation, our equivalence exercise needed to consider how criteria could be expanded and adapted for this purpose. However, SATRE v2.0 will include federation capabilities, and it is hoped the PANORAMA results will help to shape this work. Therefore, other federations will not have to address this and the columns 'critical to federation' and 'notes/justification' (figure 2) could be omitted.

The equivalence exercise workshop was held between representatives for each of the three SDEs, taking two hours to complete the exercise for the SATRE IG pillar.

Figure 3: Examples of Criteria critical to federation

Section	Item	Statement	Guidance	Importance	Critical to federation?	SDE1	SDE2	SDE3	Challenges in establishing equivalence
Information governance	1.1.1.	You must gather and monitor the information governance requirements needed to fulfil any legal, regulatory and ethical standards.	Requirements will come from a variety of sources including legislation, contractual obligations and ethical standards. Requirements must be monitored to ensure the TRE controls remain appropriate.	Mandatory	Yes	Green	Green	Green	Shared language needed to define IG framework- SATRE has not defined these terms. Challenging where evidence is not directly equivalent eg different legislation in different Nations. Also viewing the current IG frameworks is only the beginning of the process- still need to put in place a framework to enable federation, and all the IG agreements for this.
Information governance	1.1.2.	You must ensure controls are implemented to ensure the requirements are met.	Control implementation should be systematic and directly aligned to the internal and stakeholder requirements.	Mandatory	Yes	Green	Green	Yellow	What is meant by controls? Assumption is ISO 27001, DSPT etc, but this has not been confirmed. This is reflected in different interpretation of scores because lacks clear guidance on what achieves 1 or 2. Lack of SOPs is a barrier to federation so lack of SOPs outside of tolerance for this group. There is not a top-down decision on what is needed for federation, so each federation will decide what evidence is needed
Information govern	1.2.1.	You must ensure that changes to policies and standard operating procedures can only be made by trusted individuals.	It is important to ensure that policies and SOPs are relevant, up-to-date and carefully controlled to maintain the integrity and security of your TRE organisation.	Mandatory	Yes	Green	Green	Green	Description does not match the criteria - the description is essential for federation. The description is a critical part of TRE, therefore differences in this is not acceptable. All must be green for federation. Also, the statement needs to be tweaked to reflect the guidance.
Information governance	1.4.4.	You must have standard processes in place for the end of a project, that follow all legal requirements and data security best practice.	This includes the archiving of quality and log data along with the archiving or deletion of data sets.	Mandatory	Yes	Green	Green	Yellow	non-negotiable, must be all green for tolerance

Figure 3 shows an example of a subset of the SATRE criteria that were identified as critical for establishing federation across the three Secure Data Environments. It highlights key areas where achieving equivalence may be challenging and shows the tolerance levels agreed during the workshop, including criteria deemed non-negotiable and required to be rated green for federation.

4.3.1. Critical criteria with limited tolerance

Numerous criteria were identified as critical to federation, with all organisations required to be green on the heatmap: Criteria 1.2.5, 1.2.6, 1.3.2, 1.4.1, 1.4.3, 1.4.4, 1.4.6, 1.4.7, 1.5.3, 1.5.4

Whilst slight nuance in processes was acceptable, the margins of tolerance were small. This was due to the content of these criteria being key issues of data security and legal compliance, and thus, in keeping with a risk-based approach to tolerance [8], these criteria were deemed 'high risk' and so 'non-negotiable' for equivalence.

For many of these, the evidence recommended was a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), however, there is variability in both format and quality of DPIAs. Whilst it may be possible to establish equivalence between DPIAs which use different templates, federations may alternatively agree to use one specific template DPIA. This may require some organisations to duplicate assessments done in their local format and the format agreed for federation.

Similarly, where the SATRE statement references ethical approvals, the ethical approval process may vary depending on the background and location of each organisation, so additional work may be needed to establish equivalence between different ethics processes.

The only 'recommended' criterion assessed as 'critical for federation' was 1.4.7 ('You should keep a complete record of all the research studies and projects within the TRE current and past'). The PANORAMA partners also classified this criterion as essential for all partners to be green on the heatmap, as, in the UK, it is a legal requirement that all data processors keep a Record Of Processing Activities (UKGDPR and DPA 2018) [8]. Even more generally these kinds of records are becoming accepted best practice, so it is recommended that the classification of this SATRE criteria be reviewed ([appendix C](#)).

4.3.2. Critical criteria where tolerance requires negotiation

Five mandatory criteria were determined as critical for federation but where in-depth discussion and appraisal of evidence is needed to agree tolerance: 1.2.2, 1.2.4, 1.3.3, 1.3.4, 1.5.5.

For these criteria, a federation needs to decide what evidence is required, and where the tolerance limits are. These may not be the same for every federation, and will depend on factors such as existing experience working together, organisational risk appetite, requirements of data controllers and the degree of variance between different evidence types.

4.3.3. Critical criteria considered non-critical for federation

Multiple criteria were assessed as 'not critical for federation', including all of the 'optional' criteria:

- Mandatory: 1.1.3, 1.2.7, 1.2.8, 1.2.10, 1.3.5, 1.6.1, 1.6.2, 1.6.3, 1.6.4
- Recommended: 1.2.3, 1.2.11, 1.6.5
- Optional: 1.2.12, 1.4.5, 1.6.6, 1.6.7, 1.6.8, 1.6.9

The 'mandatory' criteria 1.6.1, 1.6.2, 1.6.3, 1.6.4 reference training. Whilst it was agreed that training is essential for TREs, it was felt that the requirements as written were not formally a part of 'Information Governance'. In addition, the partners' observations were that, as those criteria are currently written, it was neither essential nor practical to review evidence of this in the context of federation.

The other 'mandatory' criteria focussed on detailed elements of risk management, security controls, and operational management which were either covered by other criteria, or related to internal processes not relevant to federation.

4.3.4. Criteria lacking specificity

The PANORAMA partners noted that in some cases, they found the SATRE criteria to be very broad and there is a lack of guidance on the precise evidence required to meet a score of 1 or 2. For example, criteria 1.1.2 ('You must ensure controls are implemented to ensure the requirements are met') does not list what controls are required, leaving organisations to make assumptions about what this includes and rely on data controllers to provide guidance about the evidence they would require for federation.

By contrast, criteria 1.2.4 ('You must audit your TRE organisation against relevant requirements and standards') has clear, tangible standards and audits which organisations would reference, making the process of agreeing tolerance limits much easier.

Additionally, the PANORAMA partners found that their assumptions for what some broad criteria covered were then specifically mentioned under subsequent criteria, and the overall structure of SATRE references tangible pieces of evidence sporadically rather than systematically. Thus, it is recommended the structure of the IG pillar of SATRE be reviewed ([appendix C](#)), with broad headings for areas of IG, under which specific criteria relating to that heading would then be grouped.

4.3.5. Criteria requiring refinement

Criteria were identified where the guidance did not match the statement: 1.2.1, 1.3.4 and 1.5.6. For 1.2.1 and 1.5.6 these differences affected the decision about whether the criteria were critical for federation.

Other criteria were repetitive, with the equivalence exercise unable to discern the need to have both criteria, for example 1.4.3 was felt to be repetition of 1.4.1.

Some criteria require clarification to reduce variance in interpretation:

- 1.3.1 addresses 'risk', but with no clarity offered as to what risk/risks should be included.
- 1.2.11 references quality management of data, but this was interpreted differently as assessing the data quality itself or the organisation's data quality management system. This criterion also states that data quality is a measure of the effectiveness of a TRE, however the PANORAMA equivalence exercise argued this may not be correct.

Finally, several criteria (1.4.2, 1.5.1, 1.5.2) reference 'persons' or 'members of your TRE', but it is unclear if this includes TRE users or employees, and there was some debate between participants in order to come to a resolution about how to answer this question. Although it may not have made a significant material difference in PANORAMA partners' scores, it could potentially affect how other organisations approach federation.

4.4. Additional steps identified to create a federated IG framework

In its current format, SATRE v1.0 offers an assessment of the organisation but not of its capabilities for federation. Therefore, completing the equivalence exercise using SATRE is useful for organisations to understand each other; however, a substantial amount of work is still needed to create the framework and agreements needed to federate.

These additional steps are described in the practical guide for implementing a shared IG framework, which accompanies this report.

4.5. Designing a process to monitor equivalence over time

A final aspect that was considered as part of federation was establishing a process to monitor equivalence over time. The suggested approach from the equivalence exercise workshop is that an annual review is required to identify any changes which have occurred within the federation, and whether these are within the agreed tolerance.

In particular, this review should consider significant changes to the structure/operations of an organisation, for instance a merger between NHS SDEs. Federations may also choose to implement a formal process for adding and removing organisations from the federation, including setting a 'threshold of entry/exit' and to determine standards which must be met [2, 21].

An annual frequency for review is recommended to compliment other annual auditing requirements (for example, DSPT for NHS SDEs, ISO 27001 maintenance assessments). However, any legislative change which occurs outside of the annual reviews would necessitate immediate review by the federation.

A template for this review would help federations structure this review, and provide uniformity across the network, similar to other organisations which require an annual review [22].

A group responsible for completing the annual review should be appointed within the federation, with roles and responsibilities formally identified. This will likely mirror the infrastructure within each SDE, with Communities of Practice for each area of practice (information governance, commercial etc).

DARE UK have previously recommended the scope for a federated governance service that organisations may use or adapt as a starting point:

- Agree baseline technical standards for the Federation. This may involve defining or approving invitations to tender for technology suppliers of central Federation services.
- Agree baseline procedures for key events: onboarding a new Participant; offloading a departing Participant; etc.
- Agree baseline maturity or accreditation standards for Federation participants. This could involve setting minimum capabilities for new participants accompanied by continual improvement plans towards nationally-agreed standards.
- Agree baseline training or accreditation standards for Federation users, including service operators, Researcher PIs and other researchers.
- Manage the appointment and oversight of the Federation Services Operator.
- Approve new participants joining the Federation.

- Approve participants leaving the Federation. (This may be trumped by contractual arrangements arising from the joining process.)
- Approve technical changes with implications for, or impact on, part or the whole of the Federation, including:
 - changes to Federation standard software, for instance changes to central Federation Services software;
 - changes to document exchange protocols or formats;
 - changes to metadata standards.
- Oversee the monitoring of Federation participants' progress towards achieving nationally-agreed standards of operation.
- Oversee regular audit and accreditation for the Federation as a whole. (The practicalities of this are the responsibility of the Federation Services Operator.)

Table 2: [DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint](#): Federated governance scope

4.6. The importance of scope

One major omission in our current methodology that arose was that we did not **explicitly address the scope of the federation at the outset**. Whilst it was implied (Federated Analytics), much of the focus of the conversation did not make a distinction between a broad scope (federated pooling of data) or narrow scope (e.g. federated summary statistics). This is a critical consideration that any federation must address after agreeing on a common vocabulary and before the equivalence exercise.

In our analysis, the factors to consider when determining scope are:

- What is the analytics operation model?
- What is the organisational appetite for federation broadly, or the various types of federated analyses?
- What data analytics capabilities do the organisations possess?
- What categories of data will be included (e.g., structured data, unstructured, modalities, etc.)?
- How will legal and ethical compliance for data handling be ensured?

Clearly defining scope is crucial for implementing an overarching IG framework for federated analytics, as it ensures data controllers can set boundaries on the types of processing permitted, without limiting activity to the extent of project-specific approvals. Identifying which types of research cannot be considered within a single overarching federated IG framework is equally important, and which may require additional supporting documentation or be excluded altogether. For example, in the UK, the Information Commissioner's Office has a specific stipulation that any type of 'novel processing' must require a project-specific DPIA. Unless the federation has specific terms and conditions in place to support these types of projects (e.g. a 'call off' contract), then these would necessarily be required to be omitted from the scope of the federation.

4.7. Feedback on the revised methodology

The participants broadly recommended the use of SATRE to structure the approach to creating a federated Information Governance framework. Feedback recognised that SATRE was able to address all the IG aspects in the context of federation, with no aspects of IG missed. In addition, SATRE is applicable regardless of the setting a TRE is operating in, so could be particularly useful when federating internationally. However, it was recommended that SATRE be refined as described above. We have therefore created a reproducible, interoperable methodology that organisations can utilise to enable federated Information Governance, as a separate document.

There has been debate within the UK TRE Community about making SATRE a formal accreditation from an external auditor. Whilst this would improve the reliability of SATRE outcomes compared to the current self-assessment, due to a number of other accreditations different TREs are required to meet (for example, ISO27001, NHS DSPT, DEA, etc.), it would not remove the need for federating organisations to complete some form of discovery exercise to understand each other's processes.

Ultimately, it was observed that implementing a federated IG framework is a complex task, and is only possible with real commitment and investment from the parties involved. Compared to the ongoing federation work by the Scottish Safe Haven Network [11], PANORAMA required greater evidence from partners for their SATRE scores. This is may be due to two key differences between the NHS SDE network in England, and the Scottish Safe Haven Network. First, the English SDE network has only been operating since 2022, whereas the Scottish Safe Havens have over a decade of operating experience, delivering hundreds of research projects with no data breaches. This gives them more collective evidence, in particular mature, agreed accreditation frameworks, with which to establish trust between organisations. Second, the pilot federation project by the Scottish Safe Haven Network stems from an ambition to federate shared by all participating organisations, compared to federation as a required deliverable from an oversight body but without a clear scope or definitive approach, as is the situation within the English NHS SDE Network. Organisations approaching federated IG need to be mindful that TREs with less operating experience, and with a compliance, as opposed to voluntary, driver, may require more support and assurance to achieve success.

5. Background: The need for Federated Information Governance (IG)

Wholesale permission for federated analytics between TREs is required to streamline the processes for cross-organisation data analysis, both for researchers and the TREs themselves. This work package set out to test if the SATRE tool can be used to implement an Information Governance framework to support federation between TREs.

When defining the shared language, specific terminologies, not umbrella terms, must be defined. National-level definitions could improve unity of terminologies, but there is currently an unmet need, so it is vital that organisations agree consensus definitions to remove barriers

to federation. With the shared vocabulary established, it is essential to define the scope of federation.

SATRE is a useful tool for establishing equivalence due to its complete coverage of TRE features, and the fact it is independent of location and model of TRE. Collating SATRE self-assessments into a heatmap provides clear visualisation of areas of difference between organisations, enabling targeting discussion to determine tolerance or if treatment of difference is required. Moreover, as the assessment is already an annual requirement for TREs, the additional resource requirement compared to a new equivalence comparative format is low. However, SATRE could be amended to better support federation, through refinement of criteria, clarification of scoring, and altering the structure so specific criteria with tangible measures of achievement are grouped under broad headings within each pillar. The recommendations from this work package have been fed-back to the SATRE team for consideration for version 2.0.

To monitor equivalence over time, a federation should designate a responsible team to conduct an annual review to identify any changes within organisations and whether they fall within tolerance. Additional reviews should be held if any legislative change occurs outside the scheduled annual reviews.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

References

Where ever possible. weblinks have been used within the document.

1. Jones MC, Stone T, Mason SM, Eames A, Franklin M. Navigating data governance associated with real-world data for public benefit: an overview in the UK and future considerations. *BMJ Open* [Internet]. 2023 Oct 1;13(10):e069925. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2022-069925>.
2. Oskoui SE, Retford M, Barnes R, Postlethwaite N, Hunter KJ, Thompson S, et al. Application of federated analytics in health data research for reducing risks involved in data sharing. *SSRN Electronic Journal* [Internet]. 2022 Jan 1; Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4302481>.

3. Wang D, Shi S, Zhu Y, Han Z. Federated Analytics: Opportunities and challenges. IEEE Network [Internet]. 2021 Nov 16;36(1):151–8. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1109/mnet.101.2100328>.
4. Eden R, Chukwudi I, Bain C, Barbieri S, Callaway L, De Jersey S, et al. A scoping review of the governance of federated learning in healthcare. Npj Digital Medicine [Internet]. 2025 Jul 10;8(1):427. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-025-01836-3>.
5. Hallock H, Marshall SE, Hoen P a. C 't, Nygård JF, Hoorne B, Fox C, et al. Federated networks for distributed analysis of health data. Frontiers in Public Health [Internet]. 2021 Sep 30;9:712569. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2021.712569>.
6. Meredith PA. Generic drugs. Drug Safety [Internet]. 1996 Oct 1;15(4):233–42. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.2165/00002018-199615040-00001>.
7. Malhotra MK, Sharma S. Measurement Equivalence Using Generalizability Theory: An examination of manufacturing flexibility dimensions. Decision Sciences [Internet]. 2008 Nov 1;39(4):643–69. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-5915.2008.00207>.
8. Carpenter D, Tobbell DA. Bioequivalence: the regulatory career of a pharmaceutical concept. Bulletin of the History of Medicine [Internet]. 2011 Mar 1;85(1):93–131. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1353/bhm.2011.0024>.
9. Little TA. Equivalence testing for comparability. BioPharm International - Biopharmaceutical Science, Business Insights [Internet]. 2020 Nov 12; Available from: <https://www.biopharminternational.com/view/equivalence-testing-comparability>
10. Participation E. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (United Kingdom General Data Protection Regulation) (Text with EEA relevance) [Internet]. Available from: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/eur/2016/679/article/30>.
11. Susan Krueger Scottish Safe Haven Network's Federated Governance Pilot: Overview and Next Steps Confirmation 16 Dec 2025 [internet]. Zoom. 2025.

Appendix A: Shared Language Workshop Outputs

Table A1: Definitions of the originally listed key terminologies for a federated Information Governance framework

Terms	SDE 1	SDE 2	SDE 3	Agreed definition
Federation	Thompson (TRevolution Collaboration Café 4) defines Federation as independent organisations working together through agreed upon standards and protocols, while keeping control over their own data, services or platforms.	A group of separate organisations that have joined together to form something larger.	A grouping of organisations with their own policies and assets (e.g., datasets or computing resources) who agree to allow use of those assets by the broader group but without the assets leaving control or ownership of the organisation. (UK TRE Glossary)	A grouping of organisations with their own policies and assets (e.g. datasets or computing resources) who agree to allow use of those assets by the broader group but without the row level data leaving control or ownership of the organisation.
Ethics	The moral standard against which actions are judged.	The study of what is morally right or wrong.	Data ethics is an emerging branch of applied ethics that studies and evaluates moral problems and describes the value judgements related to data (including generation, recording, curation, processing, dissemination, sharing and use), algorithms (including artificial intelligence, artificial agents, machine learning and robots) and corresponding practices (including responsible innovation, programming, hacking and professional codes), in order to formulate and support morally good solutions (for example right conducts or right values). Data ethics encompasses a sound knowledge of data protection law and other relevant legislation, and the appropriate use of new technologies. It requires a holistic approach incorporating good practice in computing techniques, ethics and information assurance (Health Research Authority (Guidance for Confidentiality Advisory Group Applicants))	
Equivalence	Equality of processes in terms of outcome, regardless of technical variation in those processes.	The fact of having the same amount, value, purpose or quality.	The extent to which processes, procedures and policies can be seen as the same, must be defined by tangible measurable similarities.	The extent to which processes, procedures and policies can be seen as the same, must be defined by tangible measurable similarities
Tolerance	Acceptable levels of variation in processes/standards in place across different organisations.	The amount by which a measurement or calculation might change and still be acceptable.	the parameters under which differences can be accepted	the parameters under which differences can be accepted and how the measurement or calculation might change over time and still be acceptable.

Trust	The belief that an individual/organisation is reliable, able and truthful.	The hope and expectation that something is true.	the belief that another person or organisation will do what is expected.	the belief that another person or organisation will do what is expected.
Information Governance	The policies and procedures for legal and ethical management of personal data.	The intentional management of all information assets within an organisation (including structured and unstructured data) encompassing legal and compliance regulations, data security and protection, and information life cycle management.	How an organisation takes care of its information or data. It involves strategies and processes for defining, collecting, storing, securing, using, protecting and disposing of data safely, while also respecting privacy. IG ensures that data is managed well throughout its life cycle, following guidelines and laws. It helps organisations handle data responsibly, protect it from risks, and use it in a way that follows rules and keeps people's information safe. IG also identifies the processes to be followed in the event of a failure to protect personal data, and any reporting, or escalation to regulatory bodies that might be required. (UK TRE Glossary)	The intentional management of all information assets within an organisation (for all data modalities) encompassing ethical, legal and compliance regulations, data security and protection, and information life cycle management.
Data governance	The technical handling of data to ensure its security, availability and usability.	The framework of processes and policies for managing critical data assets within an organisation. It focuses on ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, availability, usability, and security of data.	Policies, procedures, and regulations that govern the collection, storage, access and use of data to ensure privacy, security, and ethical considerations are addressed. (UK TRE Glossary)	The framework of processes and policies for managing critical data assets within an organisation. It focuses on ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, availability, usability, and security of data, and that ethical considerations are addressed.

Table A2: Refined ethics definitions

Research ethics	'Research ethics refers to the moral principles and practices guiding research, from its inception through to completion and publication of results and beyond – for example, the curation of data and physical samples, knowledge exchange and impact activities after the research has been published.' (Guidance for Confidentiality Advisory Group Applicants)
Data ethics	'Data ethics is an emerging branch of applied ethics that studies and evaluates moral problems and describes the value judgements related to data (including generation, recording, curation, processing, dissemination, sharing and use), algorithms (including artificial intelligence, artificial agents, machine learning and robots) and corresponding practices (including responsible innovation, programming, hacking and professional codes), in order to formulate and support morally good solutions (for example right conducts or right values). Data ethics encompasses a sound knowledge of data protection law and other relevant legislation, and the appropriate use of new technologies. It requires a holistic approach incorporating good practice in computing techniques, ethics and information assurance. ¹¹

Table A3: Definitions of ‘Federated Analytics’

Definition	Source
<p>‘Federated analytics is a method for analysing data across multiple, separate locations without moving the raw data to a central place. Instead, a query or analysis code is sent to each data source, the results are computed locally, and only the aggregated results are returned to the user. This approach maintains data privacy, especially for sensitive information like health records, because the data itself never leaves its original location. It can also be used for training AI models, which is then called federated learning.’</p>	<p>UK TRE Glossary</p>
<p>‘A form of analytics where data analysis happens across multiple independent organisations, with each organisation keeping complete control of their own data. Instead of combining all data in one place, the analysis program or Workflow is sent to each organisation’s data For example, multiple hospitals could participate in medical research by running the same analysis on their local patient records, then sharing only the summarised statistical results. The raw patient data would never leave each hospital, but researchers could still draw insights from the combined statistical findings across all participating hospitals.’</p>	<p>UK TRE Glossary</p>
<p>‘Federated analytics’ is a newly proposed computing paradigm where raw data are kept local with local analytics and only the insights generated from local analytics are sent to a server for result aggregation. Federated analytics differs from the recent federated learning paradigm in the sense that federated learning emphasises collaborative model training, whereas federated analytics emphasises drawing conclusions from data.’</p>	<p>Wang, et al.</p>

Table A4: Additional definitions (Information Governance Framework in a Federation and Federated IG Agreement) of the derived terms in a federated IG Context

Note that these were not originally in the scope of the shared definitions, but were supplied by one of the partners as part of the definitions exercise.

<p>Information Governance Framework in a Federation</p>	<p>A structured model of policies, processes, roles, and controls that organisations use to manage information throughout its lifecycle. In a federation, this is a blueprint for how an organisation creates, stores, uses, protects, and disposes of information—in a consistent, compliant, and secure way. It’s a coordinated but distributed way of managing information. Each organisation has some autonomy, but everyone follows shared standards and policies that keep the parties aligned and compliant.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Policies and Standards. Rules for how information must be handled. (Examples: data retention policies, privacy rules, classification standards) 2. Processes and Procedures. Steps that ensure information is managed properly. (Examples: data access workflows, disposal processes, incident-response procedures) 3. Roles and Responsibilities. Who does what? (Examples: data stewards, records managers, compliance officers, IT security roles)
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	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Technology Controls. Tools that enforce IG policies. (Examples: access control systems, encryption, data-loss prevention, audit logs) 5. Compliance and Risk Management. How the organisations align with laws and reduce risk. (Examples: GDPR compliance processes, risk assessment methods) 6. Metrics and Monitoring. Ways to measure how well the IG program is working. (Examples: audit results, retention compliance, access anomalies) <p>Purpose of a Federated IG Framework: Ensure regulatory compliance; Reduce legal and cybersecurity risks; Improve information quality and usability; Support efficient operations; Enable secure and ethical data handling.</p>
<p>Federated IG Agreement</p>	<p>A federated information governance agreement is a formal document that defines how multiple departments, business units, or organizations will share responsibility, authority, and accountability for managing information under a federated governance model. It's the contract (formal or semi-formal) that spells out who does what, how decisions are made, and what standards everyone must follow when information governance is distributed across multiple groups.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shared Principles and Objectives. Why the federated model is being used. What the group aims to achieve (compliance, risk reduction, data quality, etc.) 2. Roles and Responsibilities. Defines responsibilities for: Enterprise-level IG authority. Data owners in each business unit. Data stewards. Records coordinators. Security, privacy, and compliance teams. It clarifies who has decision rights for policies, exceptions, access, and data quality. 3. Policy Alignment Requirements. The agreement specifies: Which enterprise-wide policies must be followed (classification, retention, privacy, security). What local variations are allowed. How conflicts or exceptions are handled. 4. Decision-Making Structure. How cross-unit decisions are made. How disputes are resolved. Who approves policy changes. How issues escalate. Often this includes a governance council or steering committee. 5. Data Stewardship Expectations. Sets rules for: Metadata standards. Data quality practices. Access permissions. Audit responsibilities. Reporting obligations. 6. Shared Technology & Tools. Specifies what systems or platforms must be used: Records management system; Data catalogue; Security tools Privacy (and consent, where applicable) management tools. 7. Compliance and Monitoring. Clarifies: How compliance will be measured. Who conducts audits. How findings are addressed. 8. Accountability and Enforcement. Defines: Consequences for non-adherence. Requirements for documenting exceptions. Resolutions for breaches of policy.

6. Appendix B: Full SATRE heatmap

A downloadable version is available: [Shared Heatmap for report.xlsx](#)

Section	Item	Statement	Guidance	Importance	Critical to federation?	Notes/ Justification	Evidence needed to support federation	SDE1	SDE2	SDE3	Challenges in establishing equivalence
Information governance	1.1.1.	You must gather and monitor the information governance requirements needed to fulfil any legal, regulatory and ethical standards.	Requirements will come from a variety of sources including legislation, contractual obligations and ethical standards. Requirements must be monitored to ensure the TRE controls remain appropriate.	Mandatory	Yes	Understanding of an individual organisation's framework is needed, and how they relate to each other. Need to understand the legal, ethical and regulatory standards which need to be met (especially if other organisations have different standards e.g. federations between organisations from different Nations).	Need to see each other's information governance frameworks, and all the legal, ethical and regulatory standards they need to be met.				Shared language needed to define IG framework- SATRE has not defined these terms. Challenging where evidence is not directly equivalent e.g. different legislation in different Nations. Also viewing the current IG frameworks is only the beginning of the process- still need to put in place a framework to enable federation, and all the IG agreements for this.
Information governance	1.1.2.	You must ensure controls are implemented to ensure the requirements are met.	Control implementation should be systematic and directly aligned to the internal and stakeholder requirements.	Mandatory	Yes	Need assurance that each of the partners have implemented controls required to meet the standard.	Need to define the list of controls, then evidence these				What is meant by controls? Assumption is ISO 27001, DSPT etc, but this has not been confirmed. This is reflected in different interpretations of scores because it lacks clear guidance on what achieves 1 or 2. Lack of SOPs is a barrier to federation so lack of SOPs outside of tolerance for this group. There is not a top-down decision on what is needed for federation, so each federation will decide what evidence is needed

Information governance	1.1.3.	You must ensure there are adequate resources to meet information governance requirements.	Ensuring information governance controls are suitable and enforced requires an investment of funding and people appropriate to the size of the TRE.	Mandatory	No	Need to have controls in place, but not interested in each other's resource to do this as it is difficult to define the line for what is/isn't enough resource					
Information governance	1.2.1.	You must ensure that changes to policies and standard operating procedures can only be made by trusted individuals.	It is important to ensure that policies and SOPs are relevant, up-to-date and carefully controlled to maintain the integrity and security of your TRE organisation.	Mandatory	Yes	The criteria statement is not critical, but the description is. Needs refinement so the statement and description match.	DPIA should cover this, also any SOPs for roles and responsibilities plus the policies themselves will detail the responsible person(s)				Description does not match the criteria- the description is essential for federation. The description is a critical part of TRE, therefore differences in this are not acceptable. all must be green for federation. Also, the statement needs to be tweaked to reflect the guidance.
Information governance	1.2.2.	You must use versioning and a codified change procedure for all policies and standard operating procedures.	This includes recording dates of changes, the person responsible for carrying out changes, and summary of changes.	Mandatory	Yes	This is a fundamental consequence of 1.2.1.	If all accredited and agree to recognise each other's accreditations, this itself may be sufficient. But need to provide the evidence of the policies themselves if other organisations want to see them.				Currently no underlying audit process which is specific for TREs- if there was, likely would trust meeting SATRE as evidence enough, but given no external accreditation, would currently need to see the evidence
Information governance	1.2.3.	You should measure the performance of information governance within the TRE with regular reporting available to your TRE organisation's management team.	This may include reports and dashboards showing security incidents, quality management deviations and audit findings.	Recommended	No	equivalence in other criteria would satisfy this one for federation- e.g., DPIA would include how incidents are responded to.	evidence of breach protocol, (which would also be part of the DPIA)				

Information governance	1.2.4.	You must audit your TRE organisation against relevant requirements and standards.	If you are publicly accredited against a standard, for instance ISO27001, DSPT, CE+ *etc.*, you must have processes in place to ensure you remain compliant.	Mandatory	Yes	Critical that organisations have suitable accreditations	Evidence of compliance, and appropriate responses to advice for corrections				If accreditation is achieved, then this demonstrates equivalence. But need to agree what accreditations needed- e.g. is ISO 27001 essential for federation?
Information governance	1.2.5.	You must report on and share outcomes of each audit of your TRE organisation with the required bodies.	This may include regulatory bodies or the organisations that manage accreditations you have.	Mandatory	Yes	Critical that organisations are compliant	As above, evidence of compliance				As above, I need to agree which accreditations needed. Once this is agreed, need to all be green for federation
Information governance	1.2.6.	You must ensure that suppliers, contractors and sub-contractors with access to your TRE align with your security requirements.	These should be included as mandatory, non-functional requirements during procurement and contracting. This will also include contractor staff contracts for example, legal liability and NDAs.	Mandatory	Yes	It is essential that contractors are acting within security requirements established.	Should all be documented in DPIA, though note that this depends on the quality of the DPIA				Dependent on the quality of the DPIA. Must be all green for federation
Information governance	1.2.7.	You must monitor compliance of your suppliers with the terms of the contracts.	This will include monitoring changes in the services and infrastructure being delivered and quality management within the contractor's organisation. This may be done through formal audit or by monitoring change and quality documentation provided by the supplier.	Mandatory	No	Everyone must be auditing suppliers, but do not need to see evidence of it for federation. lack of evidence would not halt the federation setup progress. Do expect the DPIAs to list all suppliers and that contracts are in place.					Needs to be altered for federation- would want assurance from DPIA that it is being done, and that all contractors are listed, but wouldn't need to actually see the evidence

Information governance	1.2.8.	You must track and maintain any physical assets used by your TRE.	All physical assets should be maintained and covered by warranty if applicable. At the end of their lifetime, assets should be securely disposed of in such a way that data cannot be recovered from them.	Mandatory (where physical assets are in scope)	No	Would want to know everyone has the right security controls etc (covered by other criteria), but do not need to investigate each other's physical assets					
Information governance	1.2.9.	You must log, track and resolve any issues resulting from deviations from processes, incidents and audit findings.	This process could, for example, be tracked through an electronic record and workflow system with records retained.	Mandatory	Yes	Essential because organisations need to know that others deal with breaches effectively	This criterion seems to be a repetition of things covered in previous criteria, e.g. about controls.				Duplication of previous statements. Have already answered about controls. Some criteria are very broad (e.g. controls one) but then later criteria go into the specifics of what would have been covered. Need categories of issues, with sub-criteria which clearly list what is required
Information governance	1.2.10.	You must use reported issues to inform changes, such as for process improvement and risk management.	All issues should be analysed for their root cause and improvements put in place to prevent further occurrence.	Mandatory	No	This is an internal process once the controls are defined.					
Information governance	1.2.11.	You should collect and maintain quality management data for measuring the effectiveness of a TRE.	Large amounts of data will be produced by elements within the TRE. These data should be analysed with reports and dashboards provided to guide TRE implementer's improvements and provide re-assurance to data consumers and data subjects.	Recommended	No	Is this asking about data quality, or data management process? Also do not feel that Data quality reflects the efficacy of a TRE					

Information governance	1.2.12.	You could use a QMS (Quality Management System) to standardise and automate quality management tasks and workflows, and to generate quality data and reports automatically.	A basic QMS could be a set of spreadsheets or documents held in a repository which are manually maintained. More mature applications will provide workflows and generate quality data through manual and automated actions.	Optional	No	Optional so not essential even within TRE (SDE)				
Information governance	1.3.1.	You must have a way to score risk to understand the underlying severity.	You have a risk assessment methodology for scoring risks on multiple axes such as impact and likelihood.	Mandatory	No	Unclear what risks this relates to. Do not need to see risk management frameworks for federation anyway.				Not sufficient for what we need to know- risks of what: controls, project management, data quality, operational risk...?
Information governance	1.3.2.	You must carry out a data processing assessment for all projects requiring a TRE.	A data processing assessment is a process designed to identify risks arising out of the processing of sensitive data and to minimise these risks as far and as early as possible. This may take the form of existing regulatory requirements such as Data Protection Impact Assessment.	Mandatory	Yes	This is the most essential criteria for federation.	DPIA (or equivalent)			varying quality of DPIAs- just having them does not mean you would trust each other. different templates between different federations, so all would need to be reviewed to ensure equivalence or would need high-level sign-off that the federation will all use one particular template.
Information governance	1.3.3.	You must have a process for designing, implementing and recording risk mitigations where indicated by a risk assessment.	Actions that are taken or not taken following a risk assessment must be recorded.	Mandatory	Yes	This is an essential part of any good DPIA	DPIA			The federation would need to review why they have scored differently and negotiate whether this difference is within tolerance.

Information governance	1.3.4.	You must have a clear set of roles and responsibilities relating to risk including who owns risks and how they are escalated and delegated.	The highest level of risk ownership is the Top Management of the TRE organisation (see Governance Roles). In order to ensure escalations to this level are rare, suitable structures should be put in place to own, mitigate and accept risk.	Mandatory	Yes	Critical to have assurance of each other's risk management process	DPIA will list roles and responsibilities				The federation would need to review why they have scored differently and negotiate whether this difference is within tolerance.
Information governance	1.3.5.	You must understand the risk appetite of your TRE organisation.	This includes understanding ownership of risk, and ability to accept risk which falls outside of the appetite should that become necessary.	Mandatory	No	The fact that organisations are seeking to federate means they are managing their own risk appetite. Differences in risk appetite will come out through the process of defining the scope of federation, so do not also require this criterion as critical.					
Information governance	1.4.1.	You must have checks in place to ensure a project has the legal, financial and ethical requirements in place for the duration of the project.	This includes checks that contracts are in place where required, adequate funding is available for the duration of the project, and responsibilities concerning data handling are understood by all parties.	Mandatory	Yes	Legal and ethical compliance is non-negotiable.	DACs (or equivalent process for obtaining appropriate ethical clearance)				Must all be green for federation.

Information governance	1.4.2.	You must have checks in place to ensure that any time limited compliance requirements are maintained.	This includes ensuring contracts remain valid and action is promptly taken should they expire. Any changes in the status of responsible persons should also be monitored, for example a data owner leaving an organisation.	Mandatory	Yes	Critical to provide assurance of compliance	For the NHS SDE network, the network user and organisational validation service would provide the required evidence. However, this depends on this definition clarifying if it relates to users or SDE employees.				Unclear if this criterion relates to TRE users or employees. Tolerance would likely be that all have to be green, but criteria needs clarifying
Information governance	1.4.3.	You must have checks in place to ensure that changes in regulations are met for a project.		Mandatory	Yes	Feels like duplicate of 1.4.1	same answer as 1.4.1				non-negotiable that all must be green, as for 1.4.1
Information governance	1.4.4.	You must have standard processes in place for the end of a project, that follow all legal requirements and data security best practice.	This includes the archiving of quality and log data along with the archiving or deletion of data sets.	Mandatory	Yes	Legal and security compliance is essential	DPIA				non-negotiable, must be all green for tolerance
Information governance	1.4.5.	You could implement a portal that can provide a workflow engine and database which automates the processes within this capability.	A portal should automate as much of the processes within the capability as possible. Where processes are automated, process maturity is easier to achieve, with more consistent completion and automatic production of quality control and monitoring data.	Optional	No	Our group did not feel this was an essential criterion for a TRE (SDE), let alone federation					

Information governance	1.4.6.	You must keep a complete record of all the data assets held within the system.	Details of all data assets (current and past) held by the system should be retained along with meta-data useful for ensuring compliance can be demonstrated. This would include ownership, data lifecycle, contracts, risk assessments and other quality data. This is likely to already exist within the wider organisation but may require augmenting for the TRE.	Mandatory	Yes	Non-negotiable that this be evidenced	DPIA				non-negotiable, all must be green
Information governance	1.4.7.	You should keep a complete record of all the research studies and projects within the TRE current and past.	The study register should contain all data related to a study including a reference to data assets, project team members, information asset owners and any compliance activities required.	Recommended	Yes	Need assurance that use of public data is being published otherwise organisations are in breach of their agreements to the public.	Evidence of register				non-negotiable, must be all green
Information governance	1.5.1.	You must have a robust method for identifying accredited members of your TRE organisation, prior to their accessing of sensitive data.	This may include ID checks or email/phone verification.	Mandatory	Yes	assuming this is users again, has been marked as critical but need clarification if its members within the organisation or users	For SDE network, this comes under the user and organisational validation network				Is this for users or employees? If for users, all must be green for federation
Information governance	1.5.2.	You must have clear onboarding processes in place for all roles within your TRE organisation.	This may include all members signing role-specific terms of use or confirming that they have completed role specific training.	Mandatory	No	Not critical for federation. Want to see roles and responsibilities clearly outlined (covered by other criteria) but do not need to see role-specific training and their records as it would be					Needs clarification about if this is employees or users, and if it is about training or contractual obligations

						checked at project level anyway.				
Information governance	1.5.3.	You must have a set of services to manage access to resources based on identity.	This will include a security model for role-based access with technical controls to ensure the principle of least privilege is enforced.	Mandatory	Yes	Access controls essential	DPIA			may be nuance in each organisation's access controls, but non-negotiable that it exists
Information governance	1.5.4.	You must not give anyone access to datasets without agreement from the Data Controller.	The Data Controller may choose to delegate this authority.	Mandatory	Yes	Essential part of meeting ethical regulations	DPIA			non-negotiable, everyone must be green
Information governance	1.5.5.	You must have robust and secure applications in place to authenticate users (and services) within the TRE.	The number of authentication applications should be kept to a minimum with common controls and standards applied across all such as MFA, password complexity *etc.*.	Mandatory	Yes	Essential controls for federation	DPIA, any accreditation standards (DSPT, ISO)			Needs discussion between the organisations to determine tolerance- e.g. password changes every 3 months vs every 6 months, can agree that is within tolerance
Information governance	1.5.6.	You must give each user of the TRE a unique logon with changes to any records strictly controlled.	The unique identifier and all associated records for a user should be traceable across the entire TRE. This will include training records, affiliations, contract agreements and ethics approvals where required.	Mandatory	Yes	Different contents of criteria statement to guidance- the statement is essential for federation; the guidance is not. It needs to be polished so that the statement and the guidance align.	Policies relating to user access			non-negotiable. Again, the criteria statement is not in alignment with the guidance. The criterion is essential, not the guidance.

Information governance	1.6.1.	You must determine what training is relevant for all roles within the TRE organisation.	This may include, for instance, cyber security training, GDPR training, and higher-level training for system operators. Specialised roles are likely to need more tailored training. Identification of these specialities should be done through a systematic training needs analysis. Specific training may also be required based on the data or information asset owner such as GCP.	Mandatory	No	Training is absolutely essential, but viewing the evidence of each party within a federation is not. In particular, trying to establish equivalence in training would be too arduous a process that it would risk de-railing federation attempts					
Information governance	1.6.2.	You must ensure that relevant training is available for all roles within the TRE organisation.	All TRE organisation members need to complete all relevant training and keep their training current. You may need to provide help or guidance to enable them to do so. Details of what training is needed will have been determined above.	Mandatory	No	Training is absolutely essential, but viewing the evidence of each party within a federation is not. In particular, trying to establish equivalence in training would be too arduous a process that it would risk de-railing federation attempts					

Information governance	1.6.3.	You must provide repeat or updated training where necessary to account for changes in competency requirements.	Training is not a one-off event. Electronic reminders for refresher training should be considered. Ideally, training should remain relevant and so policies and processes should enable people to demonstrate competency rather than unnecessarily repeating training.	Mandatory	No	Training is absolutely essential, but viewing the evidence of each party within a federation is not. In particular, trying to establish equivalence in training would be too arduous a process that it would risk de-railing federation attempts					
Information governance	1.6.4.	You must maintain accurate training records that are directly tied to the role and access levels within the TRE.	Training records should be tied to a user record and carefully maintained. Maintaining training records enables you to ensure all people have completed the required training and that repeat training happens regularly.	Mandatory	No	Training is absolutely essential, but viewing the evidence of each party within a federation is not. In particular, trying to establish equivalence in training would be too arduous a process that it would risk de-railing federation attempts					
Information governance	1.6.5.	You should accept proof of relevant training certifications from trusted third parties.	You might choose to trust certifications provided by known training providers or your institution's partner organisations.	Recommended	No	Unnecessary for establishing federation					
Information governance	1.6.6.	You could have a training platform capable of delivering online training in a variety of formats.	This could be a simple content delivery platform or a more comprehensive LMS platform. It could also include a range of multimedia delivery formats, and accessible training modules for those with access requirements.	Optional	No	Optional anyway, not necessary to view this					

Information governance	1.6.7.	You could implement a learning management system (LMS) to manage courses and deliver training as required.	Where possible an LMS should support a variety of course content and testing.	Optional	No	Optional so not required for TRE anyway					
Information governance	1.6.8.	You could ensure that any courses you use are available in standard, transferable formats.	Support for standard formats such as SCORM allows courses to be shared between providers. This could help facilitate standardisation of training provision for TRE users across organisations.	Optional	No	Optional so not required for TRE anyway					
Information governance	1.6.9.	You could keep historical copies of courses in order to demonstrate competency at a given point in time.	Information asset owners and regulators may be required to audit historical records, *e.g.* for clinical trials. It may be necessary to retain copies of superseded training along with versions of certifications within the training record.	Optional	No	Optional so not required for TRE anyway					

Appendix C: Recommendations for SATRE v2.0

During the course of these exercises, we identified several improvements that could be made to the assessment process and scoring document:

1. The scoring document should include a key on scoring. Whilst the scoring criteria are on the website, individual experts consulted may not consult the website and may misinterpret the scoring.
2. Similarly, a key for the Importance column (e.g., mandatory, recommended and optional) should also be included to help those completing the document in considering scores.
3. The scoring sheet should include a covering tab with pivot table grouped by capability and importance to help organisations easily visualise their scores.
4. The 'optional' criteria often caused confusion, as did the N/A scoring. Both of these should have further consideration to improve the effectiveness of SATRE.
5. The 'recommended' criterion 1.4.7 should become 'mandatory', or a note added that specifies that this is only 'Recommended' where legislation does not specifically require it.
6. It is recommended that the 'mandatory' criteria referencing training in the v1.0 IG pillar (1.6.1, 1.6.2, 1.6.3, 1.6.4) be re-written to make them more explicitly connected to IG, or move them from this section to 'Supporting Capabilities'.
7. The Information Governance section of SATRE should be restructured, with broad headings for areas of IG, and specific criteria then listed under each heading- the categories listed in the definition of 'Information Governance Framework in a Federation' (see Table A4 in [Appendix A](#)) could serve as the IG area headings.
8. Criteria should be reviewed to ensure the statements and descriptions align, repetition between criteria is removed, and criteria contents are unambiguous and specific.